

Heterocyclic Systems with Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom. Reactions of Cyclic Thioureas with α -Haloketones and Ketones in Presence of N.B.S.

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The reaction of 1*H*-2-mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3] diazepine(II) with 2-bromo dimedone and indane-1,3-dione in presence of N-bromosuccinimide gave 8,8-dimethyl-2,3,4,5,7,8-hexahydro diazepino [2,1-*b*] benzothiazol-10 (9*H*)-one, (IV) and 2,3,4,5-tetrahydro indeno [1,2-*d*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3] diazepine-11 (*H*)-one (V) respectively. Similarly II when condensed with α -haloketones yielded 3-substituted-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrothiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3] diazepines hydrohalides (VI). 2-Mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro pyrimidine(VII) on treatment with indane-1,3-dione in presence of NBS and α -haloketones furnished 2,3,4,5-tetrahydro indeno [1,2-*d*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] pyrimidine-10(*H*)-one (VIII) and 3-substituted-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro thiazolo [3,2-*a*] pyrimidines (X) respectively. 3-substituted-5,6-dihydro-4*H*-imidazo [2,1-*b*] thiazoles (XII) were synthesized by reaction of 2-mercapto imidazoline (XI) with α -haloketones.

THE broad spectrum anthelmintic activity of ($\pm$)-6-phenyl-2,3,5,6-tetrahydro-4*H*-imidazo [2,1-*b*] thiazole hydrochloride (tetramisole hydrochloride)¹ against *Ascaris lubricoides* and *Enterobius vermicularis* in man² and against a variety of adult and immature gastrointestinal and pulmonary nematodes in laboratory animals, poultry and livestock³ has been reported. In continuation to our earlier work on the synthesis of imidazo-thiazoles, thiazolo-pyrimidines, thiazolo diazepine, pyrimidino-benzothiazole⁴ and thiazolo pyrimidine⁵ some new tetramisole analogs have been reported in the present communication.

1*H*-2-Mercapto-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro [1,3] diazepine(II) when condensed with 2-bromo dimedone gave 8,8-dimethyl-2,3,4,5,7,8-hexahydro diazepino [2,1-*b*] benzothiazol-10 (9*H*)-one hydrobromide(III), which on neutralization with Sodium carbonate liberated the free base(IV). II on reaction with indane-1,3-dione in presence of N-bromo succinimide furnished 2,3,4,5-tetrahydroindeno [1,2-*d*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3] diazepine-11 (*H*)-one(V), whereas with α -haloketones, 3-substituted-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3] diazepine hydrohalides were formed (See Chart).

2,3,4,5-Tetrahydro indeno [1,2-*d*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] pyrimidin-10 (*H*)-one(VIII) was synthesised by us⁴ from condensation of 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-pyrimidine (VII) with indane-1,3-dione in presence of iodine. However the procedure is cumbersome and more time consuming (it requires about 30 hours of refluxing and then keeping the reaction mixture with ether for 48 hours). Hence N-bromo-succinimide has been used here in the synthesis of VIII. This considerably reduces the time period (about 6 hrs. of refluxing) and at the same time simplifies the work up. The yield is also

comparable to that reported in the previous method. 3-substituted-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo [3,2-*a*] pyrimidines(X) were synthesized by condensation of VII and α -haloketones and subsequent basification of the hydrohalide salt with sodium carbonate. 3-Substituted imidazo [2,1-*b*] thiazole(XII) were synthesised from 2-mercapto-imidazoline XI and α -haloketones following the Fefer and King's⁶ method.

Structures III, IV, V, VI, X and XII have been characterised by IR spectra (vide experimental). Lack of absorption in the region 1670-1700 cm^{-1} in compounds VI, X and XII shows the absence of carbonyl group and suggesting the cyclic structure. The anthelmintic and antifungal testing is in progress and will be reported elsewhere.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected.

8,8-Dimethyl-2,3,4,5,7,8-hexahydro diazepino [2,1-*b*] benzothiazol-10 (9*H*)-one(IV): A mixture of II⁷ (1.30 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-bromo dimedone (2.19 g, 0.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux on a steam bath for about 7 hours. The reaction mixture was concentrated and after cooling to room temperature, solid separated. It was recrystallized from ethanol in colourless needles m.p. 215°, yield 2.3 g (70%). (Found: S, 9.38; N, 8.27; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{SO}$ Br. S, 9.67; N, 8.46%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1361, 1389 (gem dimethyl), 1449 (C-H deformation in CH_2), 1550, 1608, (C=C, C=N), 1695 (C=O), 2941 (C-H stretching in CH_2), 3125 (NH).

1. 2-Bromo Dimedone, EtOH; 2. Na_2CO_3 ; 3. Indane-1,3-Dione, NBS; R COCH_3 , X, EtOH.

The above hydrobromide (1.0 g) was dissolved in boiling water and neutralized with Sodium carbonate solution to give the free base m.p., 162° (Found: S, 12.49; N, 10.91; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{SO}$; S, 12.80; N, 11.20%) $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1570, 1620 (C=C, C=N), 1670 (C=O).

2,3,4,5-Tetrahydro indeno [1,2-d] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3] diazepine-11 (H)-one (V): A mixture of indane-1,3-dione (1.46 g, 0.01 mole) N-bromosuccinimide (1.78 g, 0.01 mole) in Carbon-tetrachloride (30 ml) was refluxed for about 2 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered and the solvent distilled off. The residue was further refluxed with II (1.30 g) in anhydrous ethanol for about six hours. The dark green coloured solid was filtered and washed with ethanol. m.p. 172° , yield 45%. (Found: S, 12.24; N, 10.67, Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{SO}$: S, 12.50; N, 10.94%) $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ (cm^{-1}), 1455 (C-N stretching) 1585, 1610 (C=C, C=N), 1710 (C=O).

3-m-Nitrophenyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3] diazepine hydrobromide (VI, R=m-NO₂-C₆H₄, X=Br): Compound II (1.30 g, 0.01 mole), m-nitrophenacyl bromide (2.44 g, 0.01 mole) and anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux on a steam bath

for 7-8 hours. The solvent was distilled off and the residue crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 190° (decomp.). Yield 2.7 g (73%). (Found: S, 8.63; N, 11.44; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$ Br. S, 8.99; N, 11.80%) $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ (cm^{-1}), 730, 810, 1580, 1620 (C=C, C=N), 3100 (NH).

Other thiazolo-diazepines were prepared similarly. VI (R=m-NO₂-C₆H₄), m.p. $135-37^\circ$. Yield 81% (Found: S, 11.27; N, 14.94; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$: S, 11.63; N, 15.27%). VI (R=p-Cl-C₆H₄), 136° , 62% (Found: S, 11.84; N, 10.22; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$: S, 12.10; N, 10.59%). VI (R=2-Benzothiazolyl, X=Br), 205° (decomp.), 77%. (Found: S, 17.04; N, 11.05; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ Br: S, 17.39; N, 11.41%). VI (R=C₆H₅, X=Cl), 170° (decomp), 85%. (Found: S, 11.68; N, 10.19; Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{SO}$: S, 12.00; N, 10.51%).

2,3,4,5-Tetrahydro indeno [1,2-d] thiazolo [3,2-a] Pyrimidin-10 (H)-one (VIII): Indane-1,3-dione (1.46 g, 0.01 mole), N-bromosuccinimide (1.78 g, 0.01 mole) in carbon-tetrachloride (20 ml) was refluxed for about one and a half hour. The reaction mixture was filtered and the solvent was distilled off. The residue was refluxed

with VII^a (1.16 g, 0.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) for about 6 hours. The solid which separated at the end of the refluxing period was filtered, dissolved in boiling water and purified (charcoal). Neutralization with Sodium carbonate solution gave yellow coloured solid m.p. 212° (decomp) (ethanol) yield 1.45g (59%). Mixture melting point with the sample⁴ remained undepressed. (Found : S, 12.87 : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₀N₂SO : S, 13.22%).

3-m-Nitrophenyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro thiazolo [3,2-a] Pyrimidin (X,R=m-NO₂-C₆H₄) : It was synthesised by treating VII (1.16 g, 0.01 mole) and *m*-nitrophenacyl bromide (2.44 g, 0.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) as in the case of VI. Hydrobromide salt m.p. 217°. Yield 3.2 g (93%). (Found : S, 8.89 : N, 11.92. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₂SO₂Br : S, 9.35 : N, 12.29%). The hydrobromide salt (1.0 g) was dissolved in boiling water and on treatment with sodium carbonate yielded the free base m.p. 165° (decomp.) (Found : S, 12.04 : N, 15.61 : calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁N₂SO₂, S, 12.26 : N, 16.09%) ν_{max}^{NaCl} (cm⁻¹) 710, 810, 1590, 1620 (C=C, C=N).

Other thiazolo-pyrimidines were prepared in a similar way. IX (R=*p*-H₃CO-C₆H₄, X=Br), m.p. 230° (decomp.) Yield 55%. (Found : S, 9.33 : N, 8.41 : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂N₂SO Br : S, 9.78 : N, 8.56%). IX (R=2-Benzothiazolyl, X=Br), 257° (decomp.), 87%. (Found : S, 17.76 : N, 11.66 : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂N₂S₂Br : S, 18.08 : N, 11.87%). IX. (R=C₆H₅, X=Cl), 202°, 83%. (Found : S, 12.31 : N, 10.83 : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂N₂S Cl : S, 12.67 : N, 11.09%).

3-m-Nitrophenyl-5, 6-dihydro-4H-imidazo [2, 1-b] thiazole (XII, R=m-NO₂-C₆H₄) : It was prepared as described above by reacting XI^b (1.02 g, 0.01 mole), *m*-nitrophenacyl bromide (2.44 g, 0.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (30ml). Hydrobromide salt m.p. 275° (decomp). Yield 2.7 g.(82%) (Found : S, 9.38, N,12.59 : Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀N₂SO₂Br S, 9.75 ; N, 12.80%). The salt on treatment with sodium carbonate liberated the free base. m.p. 168-7° (decomp). Yield 90% (Found : S, 12.48 : N, 16.57, Calcd. for C₁₁H₉N₂SO₂, S, 12.95 : N, 17.00%). ν_{max}^{NaCl} (cm⁻¹) 690, 790, 1520, 1550, 1610 (C=C, C=N).

Similarly other imidazo-thiazoles were synthesized. XII (R=3,4 (HO)₂ C₆H₃, X=Cl), m.p. 235-37°, Yield 94%. (Found : S, 11.61 : N, 10.23 : Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₁N₂SO₂Cl : S, 11.82 ; N, 10.35%). XII (R=2, 3, 4 (HO)₃C₆H₂, X=Cl), 222° (decomp.), 59%. (Found : S, 10.93 : N, 9.39 : Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₁N₂SO₂Cl : S, 11.18 : N, 9.76%) : XII (R=*p*-H₃CO-C₆H₄, X=Br), 230°, 54% (Found : S, 10.07. N, 8.44 : Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂N₂SO Br : S, 10.22, N, 8.95%). XII. (R=C₆H₅, X=Cl), 215°, 65% (Found : S, 13.11 ; N, 11.29 : Calcd for C₁₁H₁₁N₂S Cl : S, 13.42 ; N, 11.74%)

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